

EVOLUTION OF WORK AND SETTLEMENTS

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Abstract

Work and human settlements are basic components of the human civilization. The types of economic activities define the advancement and can be defined as the activities and labor necessary for the survival and growth of a society and determine the kind of settlements adopted by a community. Work is essential in the provision of basic physical needs of food, shelter, and clothing. Work is ever developing with changes taking place worldwide in an accelerated fashion in the face of technological development and changing needs and wants. Work and settlements are characterized by interactions which are marked by constant cultural, political, economic, and technological change adaptations. Professions and occupations in the current world were developed from the division of labor. All the advancements in human settlements, and buildings, made by humanity over the ages can be solely attributed to the different types of work. This paper analyzes a map that characterizes different types of human settlements and work.

Evolution of work and settlements

The map is a collection of evidence of early communities of hunters/gatherers and agricultural economic activities. Hunters and gatherers are prehistoric nomadic groups that developed intricate knowledge on the life of plants, fire use and refined hunting and domestic purpose technology. The map presents a collection of evidence for the study of work to reveal the type of life, economic activities during the historical era. Work depends on the historical setting. In the prehistoric times, work could be defined as activities necessary for survival, as people worked to live. This is different from the contemporary context where, the definition work has changed to paid employment and exchange of services for money.

A number of sites the map can be classified as hunters and gatherers. The communities' involved in hunting/gathering food settled deep inside forests and forest edges. Square 1, for instance, is an open air site marked with remains of animals that were apparently hunted and slaughtered for food including deer cranium, vertebra and flint flakes as the remains of the tools used in this endeavor. The size of the area signs a small area needed to conduct post hunting activities such as slaughtering, roasting, storage and dumping etc. Site 9, 90, 97 and 99, likewise was a hunters and gatherers site marked with deer limb bones, nut shells, stone and bone tools. The nearness of the site to a spring and a cliff shows the site strategic for hunting. Site 42 harbored an advanced settled fishing community as evidenced by stone foundations, potsheds, heaps of shellfish, a market, storage facilities and processing facilities. Site 59 as well by habited by a settled fishing community evidenced by potsherds, metal fish hooks, hell heaps, building remains. Site 61 was a hunting village evidenced with deer vertebra, cranium, and flint flakes.

The community engaged in agricultural and well as hunting and tool making permanently settled near rivers and springs characterized by fertile soils and irrigation possibilities and recognized that work is critical for the acquisition of necessities and improved living standards. Site 5 was an agricultural site marked by stone foundations, broken pottery, horse shoe, pump handle, a well and hoe blade. This is an evidence of post harvest activities as well as animal rearing-horses. The well is an evidence of watering animals and crops while stone foundations shows there was a permanent settlement life style, only possible with agricultural economic activities. The same applies to site 21 with evidence of stone foundations for a permanent settlement, domestic pottery, forge and plow parts. Site 35 and 37 was agricultural community was evidenced by large grain storage and milling, pottery, stone foundations for settlement and produce storage establishments, iron smelting, sherds, large public areas, stone cut monumental

architecture. Site 49 shows a more advanced and specialized agricultural community as shown by evidence of stone foundations, wells, cisterns, wells, administrative establishments central market and grain storage as well as wagon wheels and iron implements. This is an evidence of an advanced community where work activities are essential and necessary for the production of goods and services. Site 55 was habited by a settled advanced fishing, and agricultural community as evidenced by stone foundations, turtle shells, fish weir, stone and bone tools, bone fish hooks, flint flakes, seeds, and baskets among others that emphasize these economic activities. Site 63 was a settled advanced community marked with stone foundations, pottery, kilns, grain storage facilities, and iron foundry. The same applies to sites 75, 76, 80, 82, and 98.

Work, therefore, served many functions for an individual and their community. Worked serves an economic purpose as well as social roles as the workplace provides opportunities for social interaction and friendship development. Work was also a source of social status as one is regarded on the standards of importance basis. Work represents a source of social integration and differentiation. Through work, people find a sense of purpose and establish their societal value and contribution. This community shows evidence of an advancing civilization marked by work specialization.

Site 12 was harbored a community that engaged in agriculture as well as hunting as marked with grindings stones, nut shells, deer bones, stone and bone tools, and flint flakes. The same applies to site 17 with rock shelter that face southwards, hearth, spring, stone and bone tools and deer limbs and mandibles. Site 30 as well was home to a community that engaged in both agriculture and hunting as evidenced by hearths, grinding stones, nut shells, shell jewelry, stone and bone tools, flint flakes and spring. Site 14 was a gatherers site marked with oak, Hickok trees, fragments of baskets and broken shell bracelet.

It is difficult to confusing to categorize the fishing communities as either hunters/gathers or agricultural. This is because they use a different range of tools, storage and processing facilities from the hunters and gathers and agricultural communities.

From the map, work is characteristically team work even in the early era. Work served the purposes of economic self-sufficiency, social status, self-esteem, social interchange, and social identity. Without work, one would experience alienation conditions characterized by a sensation of normlessness, powerlessness, and meaninglessness. By participating in work activities, individuals feel a sense of belonging as they take part in making the easier, failure to which one will experience isolation. With work, one finds meaning to life in their day-to-day activities, especially when the work is challenging. The inability to find work challenging makes individuals lose interest in work and, as a result, jeopardize productivity and organizational effectiveness.

The map mirrors the evolution of work and human settlement. The definition of work depends on the historical setting. In the prehistoric times, work could be defined as activities necessary for survival, as people worked to live. In the contemporary context, the definition changes to paid employment and exchange of services for money. In both olden and modern sense, work is necessary for survival as, through it, people can acquire food, shelter, clothing, and education

Traditionally, humans engaged in hunting and gathering, fishing, and agriculture of food as major economic activities. They started organizing themselves in groups to track and kill animals, work their fields and fish. Other members of society remained naturally suited to gather food. Women did not participate in hunting due to the requirements of pregnancy and nursing.

However, they took part in gathering and agriculture to increase the food value yield. This brought the need for permanent and grouped settlements. As agricultural cultivation soon replaced gathering as its yields surpassed the supply from gathering. This progress freed some people to embark on emerging economic activities such as crafting of pottery, textiles, and metallurgy, which allowed for the division of labor. Some of the people in this society also embarked on making tools and weapons for hunting and agriculture. These activities contributed to the advancement of human settlements and the need for administrative establishments.

The need to feed the growing population increased led to further innovation, such as the use of copper and bronze in tool making. The advancement gave birth to mining as an economic activity as they also laid the groundwork for a more complex society that could support the growing population.

A revolutionary change in the nature of work was born as markets and towns were established for better trade that paved the way for the development of more specialized occupations in commerce, defense, medicine, and law. The increasing complexity of these professions in the face of a growing population and increased conflict required a permanent record of history, events, and expertise, which fostered bookkeeping and writing development.

References

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